

Evaluation of perceived effects from exposure to occupational noise pollution on hearing loss among cement factory workers

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ABSTRACT

This study was designed to evaluate the perceived effects from exposure to occupational noise pollution on hearing loss among cement factory workers in Edo State, Nigeria. A descriptive cross-sectional survey design was adopted for the study, and 183 factory workers who were mainly males working at different departments in the factory, were sampled. A well designed and structured questionnaire was used to obtain personal and scientific information from the participants. The questionnaire was sectionalized into four major aspects. Background noise levels and that of the work environment was measured using calibrated Wensen WS 1361 type 2 digital sound level meter. Student t-test was used to analyse the test of association between hours at work and hearing loss; whereas the prediction of hearing loss was determined using multinomial logistic regression model. All statistical significances were considered at $p < 0.05$. The results revealed that a larger proportion of the participants demonstrated higher level of awareness on the effects of noise on health. Greater number of participants revealed higher percentage on the general use of hearing protection device; and further revealed, was that most of the participants presented high frequency of hearing loss. Participants from the storage and transportation (ST) department had the lowest prevalence of hearing loss at PTA_{512} and PTA_{346} when compared with participants from other departments. No significant relationship was established to exist between the hours at work and hearing status for both ears at PTA_{512} and PTA_{346} . The multiple regression analysis revealed no significant relationship between the selected predictors and hearing loss for both ears at PTA_{512} . However, age was revealed as a significant predictor of hearing status at PTA_{346} for both ears because a positive relationship was established between age and hearing status.

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I. Introduction

Noise has been documented as one of the bye-products of human's quest for industrialization as well as scientifically proven as an off-shoot of production

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processes called energy residual (John *et al.*, 2016). Noise pollution has been explained in different ways by different scholars to mean any unwanted and unpleasant sound; quantitatively produced by a combination of different sounds and wave lengths as well as intensities without a clear and definite composition to the ears (Ahmadzadeh, 1996). It is an unpleasant and bothering sound wave, produced by changes in the pressure of ambient air. To differentiate between noise and sound depends on the interpretation of the interest of the person receiving the sound, the environmental conditions and immediate impact generated by the sound at that particular time. At present, noise pollution has been proven to be among the physical environmental factors impacting on human's health worldwide (Ibrahim, 2016). It is a recognized threat to human well-being. In extreme range, noise can lead to human hearing impairment and has been classified by the United States Environmental Protection Agency as a serious health hazard (USEPA, 1974). In addition to its capability in causing hearing loss, noise has been scientifically documented to impact on human psychological and physiological systems including a multitude of bodily stress responses (Atmaca *et al.*, 2005).

The impact of noise on the general well-being of factory workers has been a global issue currently undergoing serious debate among scientists for the past decades (Pandya and Dharmadhikari, 2002; Concha-Barrientos *et al.*, 2004; Nelson *et al.*, 2005; Singh *et al.*, 2013; Noweir *et al.*, 2014; Lie *et al.*, 2016). Several noise exposure legislations have been enacted to limit its impact on human's health in other parts of the world. The Occupational Noise Exposure Regulation of the United States enforces industrial employers to limit noise exposure of their workers to 90 dBA for a period of 8-hours per work day (Eleftheriou, 2002). A similar maximum noise exposure dose of less than 75 dBA for a period of 7½-hours per work day was enacted in Turkey to reduce the degree of high intensity of noise exposure to workers (Republic of Turkey Ministry of Environment, 1986). Continuous exposure of extensive noise level higher than 85 dBA can impact on hearing loss; and continuous hearing loss varies from person to person depending on the frequency, duration and level of exposure (Melamed *et al.*, 2001). The impacts of noise on the general well-being of workers are physiological and psychological in nature. These impacts include any long-term or temporary lowering of the psychological, physical and social functioning of human organs (Cheung, 2004).

The perceived impact of noise in the day-to-day work operations of factory workers are of major importance to their general well-being and noise-induced hearing loss have been reported in other countries as the most common effects among the physiological impact (Singh *et al.*, 2013). Globally, hearing impairment has been reported to be the most prevalent irreversible occupational hazard associated to the day-to-day operations of factory workers. In 1995, 120 million people were reported by World Health Assembly to suffer from varying degree of disabling hearing difficulties. It has also been reported that men and women are equally at risk of hearing impairment from exposure to high intensity of noise. In developing countries like Nigeria, hearing impairment arising from occupational noise exposure

is a major public health concern that has been neglected for decades. With regard to the quest for rapid industrialization, a reasonable percentage of factory workers have been reported to suffer from occupational related noise-induced hearing loss (Concha-Barrientos *et al.*, 2004; Nelson *et al.*, 2005). Scientific documents have revealed that cement factories in industrialized nations are among the occupations with high noise levels (Kamal *et al.*, 1989; Ologe *et al.*, 2006; Lie *et al.*, 2016). However, only a few related researches have been carried out in developing countries on noise-induced hearing impairment among factory workers.

Cement production in Nigeria is important for economic development as well as development of infrastructure. In 2014, Nigeria enjoyed economic growth that was complemented with investments from the cement industry. The policy of the current administration is shifting towards the non-oil sector which entails focus on solid minerals with Nigeria having a reasonable numbers of established cement factories (Ndinwa *et al.*, 2020). The numbers of this factory is expected to geometrically increased and meet the rising demand of other African countries. However, the working condition in Nigeria's cement industry has received little or no attention with serious lack of laws protecting workers welfare (Ologe *et al.*, 2006). There are documented evidence(s) that cement factory workers run the risk of exposure to high intensity of noise at work with little or no preventive measures put in place (Morata and Meinke, 2016). Also, to our knowledge, very few researches have been carried out in this related area in Nigeria. Therefore, given the lack of studies about noise-impaired health challenges in Nigeria; documenting occupational noise exposure through scholarly studies of this nature and task that give rise to noise in cement factories are of necessity to provide working documents that will enable decision makers to ensure that measures to protect workers health are implemented. Hence, the necessity of this study doubles. Thus, the aim of this study is to evaluate the perceived effects from exposure to occupational noise pollution on hearing loss among cement factory workers in Edo State, Nigeria.

II. Study area

This study was conducted on Bua cement factory workers in Edo State, Nigeria. The cement factory is located at Afookpella, along the Abuja-Okene expressway. The factory has an installed cement production capacity of about 3.5 million MT and incorporated in 1964 as a State Government owned Cement Production Company; and sold to Bua Cement Manufacturing Company in 2008 (Ndinwa *et al.*, 2020). Geographically, the factory is located at latitude 7°16' North and longitude 6°20' East (see Figure 1). The factory services the cement demand of the south-south geopolitical zone of Nigeria (Ndinwa *et al.*, 2020). The cement factory is located in a settlement that shares boundaries with Imiegele, Kominio, Iddo, Awuyemi, Okugbe, Oku and Imekuri communities. Over the years, the factory has produced about 45 million tons of cement in excess and recognized as a giant in the employment of the local people. Bua cement factory in Afookpella has a production unit which is subdivided into: cement milling and blending, raw material crushing and processing,

clinker production, milling and packing of raw materials as well as storage and transportation sections.

Figures 1: Map of Okpella showing the cement factory, Source: Ebiagwai, (2016)

III. Material and methods

This study adopted a descriptive cross-sectional survey design to evaluate the perceived effects from exposure to occupational noise pollution on hearing loss among Bua cement factory workers in Edo State, Nigeria. 183 factory workers who were mainly males working at the different sections of the factory was sampled for the study. To qualify as a participant to be sampled, the researchers ensured that only workers whom have worked in the factory as well as being exposed to various degree of noise for a minimum of two years were selected. Also, the researchers ensured that factory workers selected as sample were entirely based on voluntary participation and personal willingness through signing of the consent form for participation. Workers with health history on ear infections, tumors, head injuries and surgeries, hearing defects and those on ototoxic medication were excluded from the sample. A well designed and structured instrument (questionnaire) was used to collect personal and scientific information from the participants. The instrument was sectionalized into four major aspects covering demographic data, general medical and hearing history of workers; level of knowledge of factory workers on the impact of noise pollution exposure and measured hearing protection device (HPD) used. To prevent participant's interference and personal influence on the data collected, the researchers ensured that the instrument was administered under close supervision.

For respondents that were illiterates, research assistants helped in reading the questions and available answers as stated in the instrument while same time, assisted in filling the questionnaire based on the response of the participants. A certified audiologist from Ambrose Ali University Specialist Teaching Hospital, Irrua was used to carry out hearing assessment and noise survey of the assessment room. Participants were assessed on a daily base before the start of work at the factory. This allowed the hearing organs to recover from any temporary threshold or fatigue that might have occurred. Instruments used were calibrated to meet standard according to the American National Standards Institute.

On the other hand, 35dB was measured by the certified audiologist with the aid of a Wensel WS 1361 type 2 digital sound level meters as the background noise level of the assessment room. The background noise level was regularly checked and monitored at least twice a day throughout the study period. This was carried out to ensure that it remain constant throughout the experiment. Otoscopy was performed with a Welch Allyn 25020 clinical otoscope to physically examine and rule out ear perforations, impact wax and ear pathologies. The mobility and pressure within the middle ear was measure using a tympanometer. A 226 Hz stimulus tone was introduced to the middle ear canal and the result plotted on the tympanogram. An audiometer set at 8 different frequencies (250, 500, 1000, 2000, 3000, 4000, 6000 and 8000 Hz) was used to evaluate each ears of the participants and the audiometric test results obtained evaluated, using the classification of hearing loss developed by Clark, (1981). Responses from the sampled participants were computed, edited, coded and analysed using SPSS version 21. Demographic data of participants were analysed using descriptive statistics. Participants' level of knowledge on effect of exposure to noise pollution from the factory was presented in percentages and measures of centrality as well as dispersion were statistically analysed and summarized in tabular format. Student *t* -test was used to analyse the test of association between hearing loss and work duration; whereas predictors of hearing loss was determined using multinomial logistic regression model. All statistical significance were considered at $p < 0.05$.

IV. Ethical clearance

Ethical approval was sought from Edo State Ministry of Health's ethical clearance and approval committee. In addition to the approval, a formal letter of introduction obtained from the Department of Industrial Safety and Environmental Management, School of Marine Technology, Burutu, Delta State was presented to the management of Bua Cement Manufacturing Company to seek permission for the study. Before the commencement of the study, the consented participants were adequately briefed with information about the study as well as the confidentiality of elicited information from the participants were assured.

V. Results

The results of the study as displayed in the various tables are presented in this section. These result details include demographic characteristics of the sampled respondents; percentage level of respondents usage of hearing protective devices (HPDs), percentage level of factory workers' knowledge on the relationship between noise and health, distribution of tympanograms among the study respondents; prevalence of pure tone average for right and left ears; and multiple regression showing predictors of hearing status for right and left ears.

A. Socio-demographic and occupational characteristics of factory workers

Table 1 present the age, educational background, marital status, departments and work experiences of the study participants. The participants ranged from 18 to 60 years with a mean of 37.5 ± 4.83 years. A higher percentage of participants 68(37.2%) fell within the range of 31-40 years; this was followed by participants within the range of 41-50 years which posses 58(31.7%) and age range of 18-30 years with 31(16.9%); whereas participants within the range of 50+ had the least percentage 26(14.2%) from the study. The entire participants used for the study were male. As observed from the data displayed in Table 1, revealed that majority of the participants had formal education with 73(39.9%) of the sample completed senior secondary school, 35(19.1%) of the study participants were first school leaving certificate holders; 30(16.4%) of them had either National Certificate of Education or the Ordinary National Diploma certificate; 27(14.2%) of the sample were degree holders, whereas participants with no formal education had the least percentage 18(9.8%). Ascertained also from Table 1, was that each of the departments had equal participants (20.2%) that were recruited for the study except for storage and transportation department with slight decrease (19.1%). More so, it was revealed that out of 183 participants studied, majority were married 89(48.6%); this was followed by participants that were single 68(37.2%) and widows/divorcees 26(14.2%) were the least among the participants.

The occupational profiles of the participants revealed that a larger number of the participants were contract staff 115(62.8%), whereas the other 68(37.2%) of the staffs were participants that were employed in the factory on a permanent bases. The data analysis further revealed that 63(34.4%) of the workforce studied had worked in the factory for 5-6 years; followed by participants 36(19.7%) whom have worked for 3-4 years; 32(17.5%) have worked in the factory for 4-5 years and 29(15.8%) of the sample had worked for 6-7 years; whereas the other 23(12.6%) participants have been engaged as staff with the factory for over 2-3 years.

B. The use of hearing protection devices (HPDs) by study participants at BUA cement factory

Workers compliance to the use of hearing protection device as reported in Table 2; revealed that higher percentage (55.8%) of the workforce studied uses HPDs while working. Despite the reported statistics, it was revealed that 41.6% of the participants had limited knowledge on the use of HPDs, 24.1% acclaimed that it was unnecessary using HPDs, 17.3% of the sample attested that the use of HPDs during work makes

them feel uncomfortable; whereas 5.2% of the participants attested that they do not work in noisy environment. These affirmations by the participants further revealed the reasons behind the nonchalant attitudes towards compliance to the usage of HPDs; as it was recorded in Table 2 that 21.3% of the participants make use of HPDs always while working; 25.8% of the sample sometimes make use of HPDs, whereas larger percentage of the participants irregularly uses the device during work hours.

Table 1. Socio-demographic and occupational characteristic of factory workers

Variables		Frequency	Percentage	Mean±SD
Age group	18-30	31	16.9	37.5±4.83
	31-40	68	37.2	
	41-50	58	31.7	
	50+	26	14.2	
	Total	183	100	
Education attainment	No formal education	18	9.8	
	First leaving certificate	35	19.1	
	Senior secondary school	73	39.9	
	NCE/ND	30	16.4	
	B.Sc/HND	27	14.8	
	Total	183	100	
Marital status	Single	68	37.2	
	Married	89	48.6	
	Widow/divorced	26	14.2	
	Total	183	100	
Employment status	Contract staff	115	62.8	
	Permanent staff	68	37.2	
	Total	183	100	
Department	RMCP	37	20.2	
	MPRM	37	20.2	
	ST	35	19.1	
	CP	37	20.2	
	CMB	37	20.2	
	Total	183	100	
Years of work experience	2-3 yrs	23	12.6	
	3-4 yrs	36	19.7	
	4-5 yrs	32	17.5	
	5-6 yrs	63	34.4	
	6-7 yrs	29	15.8	
	Total	183	100	

**RMCP = Raw material crushing & processing, MPRM = Milling & packing of raw materials ST= Storage & transportation, CP= Clinker production CMB= Cement milling & blending

Table 2. The use of hearing protection device by factory workers at BUA cement factory

Response (%)

Item	Yes		No		
HPD use during work	55.8		44.2		
Frequency of HPD	Always	Frequency	Sometimes	Infrequently	
	21.3	7.6	25.8	45.3	
Justification for irregular use of HPDs	It is uncomfortable	Never thought about it	It's unnecessary	Limited knowledge	Do not work in noise
	11.8	17.3	24.1	41.6	5.2

C. The level of workers' knowledge on the relationship between noise and health among the study sample

Investigation as displayed in Table 3 concerning knowledge level of workers on the effects of noise on health revealed that 73.2% of the studied participants reported that workplace noise levels affects workers health. Also, 26.8% of the participants objected and attested that workplace noise levels have no health effects on workers. More so, data analysis for the perception of workplace noise levels revealed that higher percentage of the participants acclaimed that they perceived the noise levels as high. This was followed by 35.6% of the participants who reported that the noise level at the factory was average, whereas 22.1% of the sampled participants acknowledged the factory noise levels to be very high. Majority of the participants representing 93.4% acknowledged that workplace noise levels impacts on the hearing loss of the workers. Further revealed in Table 3, was that 86.7% of the participants acclaimed that workplace noise level lead to headaches on factory workers, whereas 13.3% of the participant disagreed with the assertion. This was followed by 78.4% of the participants who reported as revealed from the filled questionnaires that workplace noise level easily provokes workers temper, whereas 21.6% of them disagreed. Opinion of the studied participants revealed that a higher percentage (96.1%) of the respondents consented that high workplace noise level lead to loss of workers' concentration; however, a lesser percentage (3.9%) of the sample disagreed that workplace noise level usually lead to loss of workers concentration.

Table 3. The level of workers' knowledge on the effects of noise on health

Item	Response (%)		
	Yes	No	
Workplace noise levels on health effect	73.2	26.8	
Perception about workplace noise levels	Very high	High	Average
	22.1	42.3	35.6
Effects of workplace noise levels	True	False	
Hearing loss	93.4	6.6	

Headaches	86.7	13.3
Bad temper	78.4	21.6
Loss of concentration	96.1	3.9

D. Tympanometry

Tympanometry results of the participants are presented in Table 4. A critical study of the result revealed that the entire subjects presented Type A tympanograms in 366 pairs of ears.

Table 4. Distribution of tympanograms among study participants at BUA cement factory

Category of Tympanogram	Number of ears	Percent %
Type A	366	100
Type B	0	0.0
Type C	0	0.0
Type As	0	0.0
Type Ad	0	0.0
Total	366	100

E. Prevalence of hearing loss among study participants

Table 5 presents details on the prevalence of hearing loss among study participants. From the details as contained in the table revealed that the participants' prevalence of hearing loss at 0.5, 1 and 2 KHz for the right and left ears were 8.3% across board respectively; whereas those of hearing loss at 3, 4 and 6 KHz for right and left ears recorded were 22.6% and 23.2%.

Table 5. Prevalence of pure-tone averages for right and left ears

Hearing status	Right ear		Left ear	
	PTA ₅₁₂ (%)	PTA ₃₄₆ (%)	PTA ₅₁₂ (%)	PTA ₃₄₆ (%)
Normal hearing	91.7	77.4	91.7	76.8
Hearing loss	8.3	22.6	8.3	23.2
Total	100	100	100	100
Mean±SD	13.6±11.8	21.9±8.3	12.4±7.5	21.2±9.7

Results of data analysis as shown in Table 6, revealed that at 3, 4 and 6 KHz, the prevalence of hearing loss for participants from storage and transportation department had the lowest percentage ratio (right =18.2%, left =19.7% ears) when compared with figures of the prevalence of hearing loss from other departments,

RMCP (right =22.5%, left =24.2% ears), MPRM (right =23.7%, left = 26.9% ears), CP (right = 25.5%, left =27.2% ears) and CMB (right =21.9%, left =26.4% ears).

Table 6. Prevalence of hearing loss for the various study departments at BUA cement factory

Department	Levels	Hearing Status			
		Right ear (%)		Left ear (%)	
		PTA ₅₁₂	PTA ₃₄₆	PTA ₅₁₂	PTA ₃₄₆
RMCP	Normal hearing	94.3	77.5	92.4	75.8
	Hearing loss	5.7	22.5	7.6	24.2
MPRM	Normal hearing	86.4	76.3	88.6	73.1
	Hearing loss	13.6	23.7	11.4	26.9
ST	Normal hearing	96.6	81.8	95.8	80.3
	Hearing loss	3.4	18.2	4.2	19.7
CP	Normal hearing	84.9	74.5	82.2	72.8
	Hearing loss	15.1	25.5	17.8	27.2
CMB	Normal hearing	91.7	78.1	85.4	73.6
	Hearing loss	8.3	21.9	14.6	26.4

**RMCP = Raw material crushing & processing, MPRM = Milling & packing of raw materials ST= Storage & transportation, CP= Clinker production CMB= Cement milling & blending

F. Test of relationship between the study variables

Statistics in Table 7, revealed a non-significant relationship between hours at work and hearing status at PTA₅₁₂ and PTA₃₄₆ [χ^2 (5, n = 366) = 0.62 and 1.08; p > 0.05] for right ears.

Table 7. Relationship between hours at work and hearing status for right ears

Pure-Tone Average (PTA)	Hearing Status	Hours at Work				χ^2	df	p-value
		5	6	7	8			
PTA ₅₁₂	Normal hearing	42	56	56	182	3.46	5	0.62
	Hearing loss	0	6	6	18			
	Total	42	62	62	200			
PTA ₃₄₆	Normal hearing	42	50	46	162	5.41	5	1.08
	Hearing loss	0	12	16	38			
	Total	42	62	62	200			

Significant at 0.05

Also, similar statistics as shown in Table 8, revealed as well a non-significant relationship between hours at work and hearing status at PTA₅₁₂ and PTA₃₄₆ [χ^2 (5, n = 366) = 1.46 and 1.92; p > 0.05] for left ears.

Table 8. Association between hours at work and hearing status for left ears

Pure-Tone Average (PTA)	Hearing Status	Hours at Work				χ^2	df	p-value
		5	6	7	8			
PTA ₅₁₂	Normal hearing	38	54	62	176	7.31	5	1.46
	Hearing loss	4	8	0	24			
	Total	42	62	62	200			
PTA ₃₄₆	Normal hearing	40	56	62	180	5.46	5	1.92
	Hearing loss	2	6	16	20			
	Total	42	62	46	200			

Significant at 0.05

Multiple regression analysis as displayed in Table 9, was used to test if variables such as age, years of experience, departments and knowledge significantly predicted hearing loss at PTA₅₁₂ for right ears. The regression results revealed that 4 predictors explained 8% of the variability [$R^2 = .07$, $F(4, 156) = 1.68$, $p > 0.05$] in hearing loss, which appears not to be significant. None of the variables tested significantly predicting hearing loss at PTA₅₁₂ for right ears. Furthermore, multiple regression analysis was equally carried out to ascertain hearing loss at PTA₃₄₆. This test was done to ascertain if age, years of experience, departments and knowledge significantly predicted hearing loss. The results revealed that the 4 predictors significantly explained 28% of the variability [$R^2 = .32$, $F(4, 156) = 4.54$, $p < 0.05$] in hearing loss. The analysis revealed further that age ($\beta = .56$, $p < 0.05$) as an independent variable significantly predicted hearing loss at PTA₃₄₆ for right ears (see Table 10).

Table 9. Multiple regression showing predictors of hearing loss for right ears at PTA₅₁₂

Predictors	PTA ₅₁₂				
	R ₂	Beta	B	T	p-value
Constant	.07		9.42	1.61	.51
Age		.09	.84	.62	.16
Years of experience		-.01	-.01	-.01	.69
Department		.24	5.76	1.78	.93
Knowledge		-.05	-.34	-.29	.26

*Significant at 0.05

Table 10. Multiple regression showing predictors of hearing loss for right ears at PTA₃₄₆

Predictors	PTA ₃₄₆				
	R ₂	Beta	B	T	p-value
Constant	.32		13.14	3.37	.53
*Age		.56	5.21	2.92	.71
Years of experience		-.03	-.04	-.14	.78
Department		.07	.63	.75	.82
Knowledge		-.45	-.76	-.82	.46

*Significant at 0.05

Statistical analysis as displayed in Table 11 was carried out to ascertain if age, years of experience, departments and knowledge can significantly predict hearing loss at PTA₅₁₂ for left ears. The regression results revealed that 4 predictors explained 43% of the variability [$R_2 = .39$, $F_{(4, 156)} = 2.71$, $p > 0.05$] in hearing loss; however, it indicated not significant. None of the tested variables significantly predicted hearing loss at PTA₅₁₂ for left ears. More so, same type of multiple regression test was done to predict hearing loss at PTA₃₄₆ for left ears; the results of the regression revealed that 4 predictors significantly explained 41% of the variability in hearing loss [$R_2 = .36$, $F_{(4, 156)} = 2.52$, $p < 0.05$]. The regression revealed further that age ($\beta = .44$, $p < 0.05$) as an independent variable significantly predicted hearing loss at PTA₃₄₆ for left ears.

Table 11. Multiple regression showing predictors of hearing loss for left ears at PTA₅₁₂

Predictors	PTA ₅₁₂				
	R ₂	Beta	B	T	p-value
Constant	.39		13.62	4.57	.95
Age		.31	2.48	2.73	.84
Years of experience		.15	.11	.86	.37
Department		.10	2.01	.62	.91
Knowledge		-.18	-.68	-2.06	.73

*Significant at 0.05

Table 12. Multiple regression showing predictors of hearing loss for left ears at PTA₃₄₆

Predictors	PTA ₃₄₆				
	R ₂	Beta	B	T	p-value
Constant	.36		15.07	3.35	.61
*Age		.44	5.49	2.42	.28
Years of experience		.16	.63	.17	.32
Department		-.107	-1.47	-.53	.71
Knowledge		-.15	-.92	-1.11	.26

*Significant at 0.05

VI. Discussion

Notable scholars from other parts of the world have affirmed high level of workplace noise as a known health hazard affecting the physiological and psychological functioning of human organs (Nelson *et al.*, 2005; Ologe *et al.*, 2006; Singh *et al.*, 2013). Most research surveys have focused mainly on determining the degree and prevalence of hearing loss, surveyed noise levels at workplace, assessed the relationships existing between working hours cum exposure and hearing loss. However, this study was carried out to evaluate the perceived effects from exposure

to occupational noise pollution on hearing loss among Bua cement factory workers in Edo State using pure tone audiometry, tympanometry, otoscopy and questionnaire. The survey revealed that the workers sampled were all males. This finding may be adduced to the nature of the occupation which requires physical strength for standing and operating of machineries. This finding is in line with the submission of Bisong *et al.* (2004). It also corroborates the report by Yesufu (2012) that larger proportion of male respondents take up occupation in the manufacturing industry than their female counterparts. The most prevalent age range was 31-40 years (37.2%) and 41-50 years (31.7%). This may be attributed to the fact that in Nigeria younger and experienced individuals of these age range are more needed in the manufacturing industry than any other age range. Higher percentage of the workforce sampled were literates as majority (90.8%) had one form of formal education and certification or another.

Investigation into the level of compliance in the usage of hearing protection devices among the participants was essential because of the opportunity to understand and amend the inadequacies in noise exposure reduction efforts in the factory. The survey analysis revealed that workers percentage level on the general usage of hearing protection devices was high. This finding was ascertained as 55.8% reported its usage during working hours. Specifically, 21.3% of the participants make use of HPDs always; this was followed by 25.8% of the sample which claim to sometimes make use of the device; however, larger percentage (45.3%) of the participants irregularly uses the device during working hours. The study further revealed that 41.6% of the participants had limited knowledge on the use of hearing protection devices; 24.1% acclaimed that the use of HPDs was unnecessary, 17.3% attested that using HPDs during work hours make them feel uncomfortable, whereas 5.2% confirmed not to work in noisy environment as the reason behind their non usage of HPDs. The reasons adduced by the participants revealed their level of awareness and understanding on the benefits of HPDs. These results are similar with the results reported by Ali *et al.* (2012). They reported 14.5% for unavailability of HPDs, 6.6% for HPDs not necessary, 11.8% for discomfort and 2.6% for limited knowledge. These findings also affirmed the results reported by Mndema and Mkoma (2012) that about 15% of workers in Tanzania cement factory do not always make use of HPDs because they lack proper awareness and understanding of its effective on the protection of hearing organs. More so, similar findings were reported in a survey research conducted on firefighters and documented by Hong *et al.* (2008). NIOSH (1998) mandated employers to train and retrain workers on how to appropriately select, fit and use hearing protection devices. The findings of this study necessitate the urgent need for occupational and safety laws that would ensure that employers protect their employees by providing the necessary safety gadgets and equipment as well as enforcing compliance on usage among employees. Furthermore, the design and implementation of an awareness and training programs to further educate workers on the benefits of using HPDs and other safety gadgets as well as the demerits would go a long way to curb occupational injuries and disabilities.

This study revealed that a sizeable percentage of the participants at the cement factory studied exhibited in-depth knowledge on the impact of noise on workers' health. This was made known as the results displayed in Table 3 confirmed that 73.2% as against 26.8% of the studied participants reported that workplace noise levels affect workers health. More so, the data which sought to enquire on the participants' perception of workplace noise levels revealed that majority perceived noise level as high. Responses from the participants also revealed that larger proportion of the sample representing 93.4% acknowledged that workplace noise level impacts on the hearing loss of workers. Furthermore, 86.7% of the participants acclaimed that workplace noise levels caused headaches, 78.4% affirmed easy provocation of worker's temper and 96.1% consented to loss of worker's concentration. The overwhelming responses of the participants could be as a result of the workers experiencing such effects from workplace noise levels. This report affirmed the findings by Bisong *et al.* (2004); Yesufu (2012) and Ali *et al.* (2012). It was also in conformity with the figures; 20.5% for headaches, 53.8% for hearing problems and 17.9% for irritability as a result of exposure to workplace noise which was reported by Mndema and Mkoma (2012). The finding from the study as well revealed that higher percentage of the participants were knowledgeable on the preventive measures such as work rotation; however, the practice of these measures was not reflected in their day-to-day task.

Also worthy of notice is that the entire study participants were subjected to middle ear evaluation with tympanometer. The result revealed that the participants' ears tested were presented with Type A tympanograms. This was a confirmation of normal middle ear pressure and tympanic membrane mobility in the ears tested.

Pure tone audiometry was carried out to assess the ears of 183 participants. The audiometry was done on both ears of the participants. The PTA was calculated over a frequency of 0.5, 1 and 2 KHz for both ears and the PTA for the ears was added up and then hearing values compared to standard (≤ 50). The prevalence of hearing loss at PTA₅₁₂ (0.5, 1 and 2 KHz) was revealed to be 8.3% for right and left ears as well as 22.6% for right ears and 23.2% for left ears at PTA₃₄₆. This finding revealed that most of the participants are presented with a high frequency of hearing loss. Shakhathreh *et al.* (2000) in a study carried out among workers in a textile factory revealed elevated levels of hearing loss among respondents with continuous exposures. Their report revealed an increase in hearing loss (39%) among workers who had worked for 25 years or more in the textile factory. In a similar study by Osibogun *et al.* (2000), a significant hearing loss among workers exposed to noise in a textile factory in Logos was recorded. Their findings revealed significant threshold shifts at 4000 Hz among the group exposed to noise. Also, a positive correlation between increased hearing threshold levels and duration of exposure were reported. Boateng and Amdofu (2004) in a study determined the effects of industrial noise pollution on the hearing acuity of workers in Ghana. They reported the prevalence of hearing loss to be 23%, 20% and 7.9% among respondents at corn mills, saw mills

and printing press respectively. It was revealed in their study, that noise levels at saw and corn mills exceeded 90 decibels.

Participants from storage and transportation (ST) department had the lowest prevalence of hearing loss at PTA₅₁₂ and PTA₃₄₆ when compared with participants from other departments. This may be adduced to the degree in levels of noise exposure in the aforementioned departments. This finding was consistent with the report by Yabani (1995); who reported a significant higher prevalence of hearing loss among employees of a milling department. No significant relationship existed between the hours at work and hearing status for both ears at PTA₅₁₂ and PTA₃₄₆. This may be attributed to the fact that majority of the study participants have not worked more than 6 years in the factory. This finding was not in conformity with the report by Yabani (1995); who demonstrated that workers who spent at least 5 years in cement manufacturing company exhibited symptoms of noise induced hearing loss. Further revealed from the regression analysis was that no significant relationship existed between the selected predictors and hearing loss for both ears at PTA₅₁₂. However, age was revealed as a significant predictor of hearing status at PTA₃₄₆ for both ears. The relationship established between age and hearing status was positive. The implication of this finding was that older workers presented more severe hearing loss than the younger counterparts. Noticeable researchers in other parts of the world have demonstrated similar findings of hearing loss due to ageing. However, it has remained unclear and difficult to ascertain till date, the relationship between noise-induced hearing loss and age-related hearing loss. This may be due to the fact that age-related hearing loss is caused by several factors (Rosenhall, 2003).

VII. Conclusion

This cross-sectional survey study sought to evaluate the perceived effects from exposure to occupational noise pollution on hearing loss among Bua cement factory workers in Edo State, Nigeria. The study specifically evaluated the percentage ratio of compliance on the use of hearing protection devices by workers during working hours, worker's level of awareness on the effects of noise, attitude of workers toward the use of hearing protection device, prevalence of hearing loss among workers, relationship between years of engagement at the factory and hearing status of workers. The results from the analysis of field data revealed that a larger proportion of the study participants demonstrated higher percentage level of awareness on the effects of noise on health. Greater number of participants revealed higher percentage on the general usage of hearing protection device; and further revealed, was that most of the participants presented high frequency of hearing loss. Participants from the storage and transportation (ST) department had the lowest prevalence of hearing loss at PTA₅₁₂ and PTA₃₄₆ when compared with participants from other departments. No significant relationship was established to exist between the hours at work and hearing status for both ears at PTA₅₁₂ and PTA₃₄₆. Further revealed from the multiple regression analysis was that no significant relationship existed between the selected predictors and hearing loss for both ears at PTA₅₁₂. However, age was revealed as a

significant predictor of hearing status at PTA₃₄₆ for both ears because a positive relationship was established between age and hearing status.

VIII. Recommendations

The following recommendations were made by the researchers based on the findings of the study

1. Workers should be equipped adequately with effective and functional hearing protection devices.
2. Workers engaged in departments where noise level exceeds 100 dB should be provided with double fitted hearing protection devices to sufficiently reduce the effects from the exposure.
3. Routine training programmes should be developed and implemented by employers in order for workers to be equipped intellectually on the benefits of practicing safety at work
4. Employers should ensure that workers are effectively monitored on the use of hearing protection devices and as well spell out penalties for defaulters.
5. Pre-employment and post employment assessment of workers hearing organs should be carried out effectively.

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